

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant. Part II. Partial Molal Volume of Some Uni-univalent Electrolytes in Formamide

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The work on partial molal volumes of electrolytes in formamide has been extended to some more uni-univalent electrolytes. The data obtained, in conjunction with those for sodium, potassium, and ammonium salts of monobasic acids, reported earlier¹, have been used to determine the ionic contributions to partial molal volume $\bar{V}_0$ of different electrolytes.

The values of $\bar{V}_0$ for different electrolytes have been found to be slightly larger in formamide than the corresponding values in water.

Preliminary work on the partial molal volumes of eleven uni-univalent electrolytes in formamide has already been reported¹. The work has been extended to some uni-univalent electrolytes of less common type and slightly more difficult to handle on account of their high hygroscopic nature, e.g., rubidium and cesium halides and nitrates and lithium chloride. This was essential in order to obtain a more general picture of the partial molal volumes in formamide and to be able to correlate them with the properties of the electrolytes. The present communication records the partial molal volume data at finite dilution, i.e., $\bar{V}_0$ of the electrolytes mentioned above.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental procedure was the same as described in the earlier communication¹. Care was taken to exclude moisture from the weighing system and the densities were determined with capped pycnometers. The apparent molal volumes at different concentrations, $\bar{V}$, calculated from the corresponding densities in the usual manner, were plotted against $\sqrt{C}$ and then the resulting curve was extrapolated to zero concentration to obtain the partial molal volume at infinite dilution, i.e. $\bar{V}_0$, as required by Masson's equation²:

$$\bar{V} = \bar{V}_0 + S_V \sqrt{C}$$

The $\bar{V}$ vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves for different electrolytes are shown in Fig. 1.

The values of $\bar{V}_0$ for different electrolytes, obtained from Fig. 1, are recorded in Table I. The $\bar{V}_0$ values for a few other electrolytes, reported earlier¹, are also reproduced in Table I for ready reference. In order to have a comparative idea, $\bar{V}_0$ values of different

1. Gopal and Srivastava, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 2704.

2. *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, vii, 3, 218.

electrolyte, in water³ are also included in Table I. The slope, S_V , of the straight line curves ($\bar{V}$ vs. $\sqrt{C}$), both in formamide and water, are shown in columns 3 and 5 of Table I.

FIG. 1. Apparent molal volumes of salts in formamide.

It may be observed from Table I that the $\bar{V}_0$ for any electrolyte in formamide is slightly larger than the corresponding value in water. It is well known that $\bar{V}_0$ values in water are additive. The same is found to be true in formamide solutions (vide Table II).

From the examples shown in Table II and in the communication referred to earlier¹, the values of $\bar{V}_0$ in formamide, as in water, are strictly additive and hence can be divided

3. Harned and Owens, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 3rd. ed., Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, N.Y., 1958, p. 361.

into two contributions, one corresponding to the cation and the other to the anion of which the electrolyte in question is made. Several methods have been suggested by different workers for this purpose. Thus Fajans and Johnson⁴ considered that NH_4^+ and Cl^- ions contributed equally to $\bar{V}_o$ of NH_4Cl and hence

$$\frac{1}{2} \bar{V}_o(\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}) = \bar{V}_o(\text{NH}_4^+) = \bar{V}_o(\text{Cl}^-).$$

TABLE I

Temp. = 25°.

Electrolyte.	Formamide		Water	
	$\bar{V}_o$.	S_v .	$\bar{V}_o$.	S_v .
LiCl	19.60 ml	1.36	17.00 ml	1.490
NaCl	21.10	1.60	16.40	2.133
NaBr	28.00	1.18	23.51	1.760
NaI	39.85	0.93	35.10	1.346
NaNO ₃	33.55	1.55	..	..
KCl	32.00	0.86	26.52	2.327
KBr	38.90	0.43	33.73	1.919
KI	59.75	0.39	45.36	1.556
KNO ₃	44.10	0.73	38.19	2.300
RbCl	35.90	0.82	31.87	2.219
RbBr	42.60	0.48	39.71	2.038
RbI	54.65	0.46	50.30	1.607
RbNO ₃	48.25	0.78	..	..
CsCl	42.30	0.79	39.15	2.172
CsBr	49.30	0.48	46.19	1.901
CsI	61.05	0.34	57.74	1.579
CsNO ₃	54.65	0.697	..	..
NH ₄ Cl	37.20	1.31	35.98	1.450
NH ₄ Br	44.05	0.50	..	..
NH ₄ NO ₃	49.24	0.83	47.56	0.970

*From Harned and Owens:³

TABLE II

$\bar{V}_o(\text{CsCl}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbCl}) = 6.40$ ml	$\bar{V}_o(\text{CsI}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{CaNO}_3) = 6.40$ ml
$\bar{V}_o(\text{CaBr}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbBr}) = 6.70$	$\bar{V}_o(\text{RbBr}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbCl}) = 6.70$
$\bar{V}_o(\text{CaI}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbI}) = 6.40$	$\bar{V}_o(\text{CaBr}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{CsCl}) = 7.00$
$\bar{V}_o(\text{CaNO}_3) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbNO}_3) = 6.40$	$\bar{V}_o(\text{RbI}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbCl}) = 18.75$
$\bar{V}_o(\text{RbI}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{RbNO}_3) = 6.40$	$\bar{V}_o(\text{CaI}) - \bar{V}_o(\text{CsCl}) = 18.75$

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 668.

On this basis the partial molal volumes of different ions were computed. The difficulties and objections to this and to some other methods of division have been recently discussed by Mukerjee⁵ who has assumed, as is implicit in the work of Couture and Laidler⁶ as well as of Bernal and Fowler⁷, that for large monatomic monovalent ions of inert gas structure, the $\bar{V}_0$ does not depend on the sign of the charge but only on the cube of their respective radius. Although the method mentioned earlier⁴ and others have some points of interest and justification, the method suggested by Mukerjee⁵ has been employed here due to its simple and appealing assumption. The value of $\bar{V}_0$ of cesium iodide has been first divided into respective contributions of cesium and iodide ions. The values of $\bar{V}_0$ of other ions have been obtained by subtraction of $\bar{V}_0(\text{Cs}^+)$ or $\bar{V}_0(\text{I}^-)$ from the $\bar{V}_0$ of the appropriate electrolyte. These are shown in column 3 of Table III.

TABLE III

Partial ionic volumes of some univalent ions.

Ion.	Crystal radius* ($r_0 \times 10^8$ cm).	$\bar{V}_0$ (ion).	$\bar{V}_0$ (ion). (corrected graphically).
Li^+	0.60	-2.94 ml	..
Na^+	0.95	-1.44	..
K^+	1.33	9.46	8.66 ml
Rb^+	1.48	13.36	12.56
Cs^+	1.69	19.77	18.97
NH_4^+	1.42	14.66	..
Cl^-	1.81	22.54	23.34
Br^-	1.95	29.44	30.24
I^-	2.16	41.29	42.09
NO_3^-	1.21	34.64	..

*Pauling's radii.

If these $\bar{V}_0$ values of different ions are plotted against the corresponding r_0^3 , r_0 being the crystallographic radius of the ion concerned, different cations appear to fall on one line and anions on the other. The same line can be made to pass through most of them if 0.8 ml is subtracted from the calculated $\bar{V}_0$ values of cations and added to those of anions, as is clear from the curves shown in Fig. 2. These corrected values of $\bar{V}_0$ of different ions are shown in column 4 of Table III.

The smaller ions like Na^+ and Li^+ are not expected to obey the simple assumption on account of high ion-solvent interaction.

The $\bar{V}_0$ of the nitrate ion in formamide is only slightly larger than the corresponding value in water. Due to asymmetric nature of the ion, it is not possible to assign any definite radius to it and hence its position on the graph is indefinite.

5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 740, 744.

6. *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1956, 34, 1209; 1957, 35, 207.

7. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, 1, 532.

FIG. 2. Partial molal volumes of ions vs. $c^{1/2}$.

The Values of S_v .—In view of the fact that extrapolation to infinite dilution in Fig. 1 has been made from the higher concentrations ($\bar{V}$ vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves), it is not expected to use these values of S_v to test the Redlich equation⁸, namely

$$S_v = R \left(\frac{2e^2}{Dk} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi N}{1000T} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left\{ \frac{1}{D} \frac{dD}{dP} - \frac{\beta}{3} \right\}$$

(where e is the electronic charge; D , the dielectric constant; k , the Boltzman factor, N , the Avogadro number; T , the absolute temperature; β , the compressibility; P , the total pressure). The factor $(1/D)^{3/2}$ outside the square brackets will reduce the values of S_v to about 7/11 to that in water. Although the values of S_v in formamide are less than the corresponding values in water (Table I), it will be premature to make any definite comments in view of the unknown values of (dD/dP) and β for formamide.

The determination of $\bar{V}_o$ for other electrolytes, containing bivalent and trivalent ions in formamide, is called for before a detailed study of the ion-solvent interaction in formamide, specially the electro-contraction effect of ions, can be undertaken. It is proposed to obtain these data as soon as possible.

One of the authors (R.K.S.) is grateful to U.P.S.R.C., for the grant of a fellowship. Their thanks are also due to the Head of the Chemistry Department and the authorities of the Lucknow University for providing necessary facilities in carrying out this investigation.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received July 26, 1962.